

**STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ORGANIC COSMETIC
PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE**

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ABSTRACT

Looking at the world today, organic food products obtaining popularity to a greater extent among the people because their faith is that organic food products are hygienic, harmless and disease free compared to the conventional food products. Accordingly, the demands for organic food products are increasing constantly. In addition, the consumers' awareness with regard to negative consequences caused by the conventional food products gradually drives the consumers to go for organic food products. This paper attempts to study the various factors which influence the consumers to buy organic food products. The structured questionnaire was administered during the study with a total sample size of 150. The SPSS tool has been applied to analyze the data collected from the consumers of organic food products. The study has been concluded various factors namely good in taste and more hygienic, no preservatives, more nutritious, fresh and safe, vital role in diet chart, non-contamination, good packaging, good quality and quantity and healthy lifestyle that are to influencing consumers to purchase organic food products.

Keywords: Organic Food Products, Purchasing Habits, Healthy Lifestyle, Consumption Habits

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the people are more tending towards healthy way of living. Hence, the significance of organic food products is gaining popularity among the population. In India, a lot of organization continuing to introduce many forms of organic food products and packaging programs by way of introduction of new and useful green products and packages. In reality, organic food business plans are the fastest growing cookery trend around the world. Consumers are becoming more tactful in their purchasing attitudes towards food products and also the preferences of consumers to purchase organic food products and services are increasing nowadays. In general organic food products are more expensive to buy than the conventional food products. Even so the consumers are ready to pay higher price for organic food products, which will contribute more opportunities to the organic food companies. A better understanding of purchasing habits of consumers will empower the organic food companies to obtain market opportunities. In this consideration, there are various factors that affect the purchasing habits of consumers. The main aim of this study is to know about the factors influencing consumers of organic food products in Coimbatore city.

I. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

During the past decades, there were remarkable changes in Indian food industry due to the changes in socio economic development. The consumers concern towards food consumption habits and environmental issues are improving day by day. Consumers are familiar about the organic food products carry benefit in terms of health and impart energy to the user. Because of this positive change in the consumption habits of people, initiatives by organic food companies and governments putting their great efforts to serve the people healthy and to save the environment as well. There are number of studies that look into the consumer belief on organic food consumption, however this study focus to determine the factors influencing consumers of organic food products in Coimbatore city.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the socio-economic profile of the consumers.
- To study the factors which influence consumers to purchase organic food products.

III. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The main scope of this study is to figure out the main factors that can influence organic food purchase habits among consumers in Coimbatore city. This study will help the marketers to develop strong strategies influencing not only consumer perspective and buying intention but also actual purchase behavior. Hence, the result of this study may provide useful information for organic food marketers to frame successful marketing policies.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

R. Krishna and P. Balasubramanian (2018) made a study on “The Significance of Factors Influencing Consumer Behaviour towards Organic Food Products in Kochi”. The main objectives of the study were to analyze the purchase behavior, preferences and factors affecting the consumer’s purchase intention towards organic food products. The retail stores for organic food products alone are considered for the study. Purposive sampling method has been used for the primary data collection. The data was collected with the help of structured questionnaire from the customers who visited supermarkets either regularly or occasionally which has organic food sections in it and also from exclusive organic food stores located in Kochi. The result shows that lack of effective distribution and promotion systems among organic products has created a major influence on the familiarity as well as on accessibility. Marketers need to bring out innovative strategies for retaining the customers and in turn convert them into loyal customers. The perceptions of this research can be useful to the marketing managers to decide on their market segments and thereby target the potential consumers.

Chaitra Bharath and H.M. Chandrashekar (2018) in their article entitled “A Study on the Consumer Awareness of Organic Certification of Food Products in Mysore City” made an attempt to evaluate the awareness among organic food consumers regarding the certification of organic food in Mysore city. The data had been collected randomly from 75 consumers of organic food products conducted in both generic super markets and organic retail outlets. The result shows that the consumers are still in the adoption stage because the consumers noticed the benefits very slowly. Government should take necessary steps to conduct awareness programmes in such a way that all segments of consumers should understand the significance of certification of organic food and its impact on their lives.

Dasari.Pandurangarao, Dr.K.Chiranjeevi and Prof.D.Suryachandra Rao (2017) in their study analyzed factors affecting consumers to buy organic food products in Hyderabad and Secunderabad, India. A sample of 500 consumers was interviewed using structured questionnaires to examine key factors influencing them to use organic food. The data obtained from the survey were analyzed with percentage method, reliability test, and factor analysis. The results revealed that ten factors such as labels, health, concern, environment concern, brand advertising, safety, accessibility, affordability, freshness and store location that are influencing customers to buy organic food. Out of these, health, environment and safety are key factors that are found as primary influencers. Significant relation is found between buying behavior and environment concern. Hence, study made conclusion that health, safety and environment are key reasons why people buy organic food products.

V. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

In this study, the data has been collected from the consumers of organic food products in Coimbatore city. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. The primary data has been obtained by administering a structured questionnaire to consumers of organic food products in Coimbatore city. The secondary data has been collected from various sources such as magazines, journals, websites etc. Convenience Random sampling technique has been adopted to select respondents for the study. The data has been collected from 150 consumers of organic food products.

Tools used

The following statistical tools have been used to analyze the data with reference to the selected objectives of the study.

- Percentage analysis
- Descriptive analysis
- t – Test

VI. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Data analysis is the most pivotal component of research. Without analysis and findings, generalization and prediction cannot be achieved which is the target of the research.

From the above table, 68.7 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 31-40 years and 3.3 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 18-20 years. With respect to gender of the respondents 83.3 percent of the respondents are female. Generally, female have more conscious in health and also have knowledge regarding the purchase of food products. Out of total respondents, majority of the respondents are married. In the study area majority 60 percent of the respondents are graduates. Regarding monthly income, 62.7 percent of the respondents have income below Rs.15,000. 46.7 percent of the respondents have good knowledge on organic food products. Hence, most of the people have awareness on organic food products. 97.3 percent of the respondents agree that an organic food product improves the health. It is seen that 55.3 percent of the respondents use the products partially whereas 44.7 percent of the respondents use the products regularly. In many stores the availability of organic products is less compared to other products. Therefore, the major obstacle faced by the respondents is availability.

It is seen from the above table that the highest mean rating is 4.39 for the item “More nutritious than conventional food “. That is on average; the agreed levels of the respondents are between strongly agree and agree. The items such as “Good in taste and more hygienic”, “Non-contamination”, “Consumption results in healthy lifestyle”, “Play a vital role in a diet chart”, “Good quality and quantity”, “Generally fresh and safe”, “No preservatives” had the agreed level of the respondents is between strongly agree and agree. “Marketing of it is creative and attractive” has the mean rating of 3.88 which is slightly high. “Good packaging” has the mean rating of 3.83 which is slightly higher than the item “Cultural reasons or family traditions”. It has mean rating of 3.75. The lowest mean rating is 3.55 for the item “Using it is a part of status symbol”. That is on average, the agreed level of the respondents is between agree and neutral.

Socio Demographic Factors Vs Factors Influencing Consumers to buy Organic Food Products

ANOVA and t-test are used to analyse whether there is a significant difference between the socio demographic factors and factors influencing organic food products.

H0: There is no significant difference between socio demographic factors namely age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, using of organic food products and factors influencing consumers of organic food products.

NS - Not significant * -Significant

It is seen from the above table that the mean score is found to be high (4.10) among the age group of respondents between 18-20 years and found to be low (3.73) among the age group of respondents between 30-40 years. The mean score is found to be high (4.12) for male respondents and to be low (4.06) for female respondents. With regard to marital status, the mean score is found to be high (4.09) for unmarried respondents and found to be low (3.96) for married respondents. In case of Educational qualifications, the mean score is found to be high (5.00) for primary education and found to be low (3.87) for post graduate. In case of using organic food products, the mean score is found to be high (4.24) for regular usage and found to be low (3.93) for partially usage.

The ANOVA result shows that there is no significant difference between the mean score of the factors influencing consumers of organic food products and socio demographic factors namely age and educational qualifications. Hence the null hypothesis has been accepted at 5 percent level of significance.

The t-test results show that there is no significant difference between the mean score of the factors influencing consumers of organic food products and socio demographic factors namely gender and marital status. Hence the null hypothesis has been accepted at 5 percent level of significance. It is also seen that there is significant difference between factors influencing consumers of organic food products and using of organic food products. Hence the null hypothesis has been rejected.

VII. SUGESSTIONS

It is recommended that the government needs to support for the development of organic farming and for the growth of organic food market facilities through financial support and by framing various policies. At the same time the awareness should be created among the general public about the health benefits and usage of organic food products. A marketer needs to promote the benefits of organic food products among the consumers to increase market size.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Today the awareness about the organic food products have been generated among the people, hence the proper availability and affordability were provided to the consumers then the demand will increase in future. Organic food products are accessible in major cities. This study states that the majority of the people agree that an organic product improves the health. The main obstacles faced by the respondents are availability and then affordability. The study has been concluded various factors namely good in taste and more hygienic, no preservatives, more nutritious, fresh and safe, vital role in diet chart, better quality and non-contamination, good packaging, good quality and quantity and healthy lifestyle that are to influencing consumers to purchase organic food product.

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